

Influence of oxygen vacancies on structural and electrical properties ferromagnetism imposed ferroelectric material

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Abstract

BaTi_{1-x}Fe_xO_{3-δ} ceramics have been prepared by solid state reaction route. Effect of oxygen vacancies on structural and electrical properties of Fe-substituted BaTiO₃ is investigated. From Rietveld refinement, tetragonal (P4mm) and orthorhombic (Amm2) phases occur in pure BaTiO₃ [1] while tetragonal (P4mm) and hexagonal (P6₃/mmc) in Fe-substituted BaTiO₃. Cell parameters, volume fraction and oxygen vacancies are also obtained from Rietveld refinement. Hexagonal unitcell was drawn using VESTA. Ti1(2a) and Ti2(4f) are located in the center of corner-shared TiO₆ octahedra and face-shared Ti₂O₉ dimer respectively. Leakage current is increased almost 2 orders of magnitude in Fe-substituted BaTiO₃ than pure BaTiO₃ which is due creation of oxygen vacancies for charge compensation. Calculated δ values are 0.188 and 0.282. Present work revels that oxygen vacancies play an important role in structural and electrical properties of ferromagnetism imposed in a ferroelectric material.

Keywords: BaTiO₃, Rietveld refinement, oxygen vacancy, multifunctional material.

Reference

- [1] B. Bagyalakshmi et al, Materials Letters, 170 (2016) 48-52.

